

NOUN OF THE 3^d DECLENSION (FEMININE GENDER)

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Abstract. The article talks about the 3rd declension in Latin and Greek, giving importance on the challenge of identifying these nouns due to diverse stems and ambiguous nominative forms. It highlights the use of the genitive singular ending '-is' but notes exceptions, and therefore it makes the third declension nouns less predictable if we are comparing it to the first and second declensions.

Key words: third declension, case formation, athematic, genitive singular, gender ambiguity, and declining nouns.

Introduction. The third declension is a category of nouns in Latin and Greek with broadly similar case formation — diverse stems, but similar endings. Sanskrit also has a corresponding class (although not commonly termed as third), in which the so-called basic case endings are applied very regularly.

In contrast with the first- and second-declension endings, those of the third declension lack a theme vowel (a or o/u in the first and second declensions) and so are called athematic.

Many third-declension nouns, unlike first- or second-declension nouns, show different stems depending on case and number — usually one stem for the nominative singular, and another for the rest of the cases, though some Greek nouns have three stems.

A subcategory within both the Latin and Greek third declension is nouns with consonant stems. These, unlike all first- and second-declension nouns, end in a consonant. Often the consonant at the beginning of certain endings undergoes a sound change with the consonant of the stem.

Main Body.

You can identify third declension nouns by their genitive singular ending '-is'. You cannot identify third declension nouns in the nominative because they,

- have various forms and spelling
- have endings that do not reveal their gender can be masculine, feminine or neuter.

To decline a third declension noun:

find the genitive singular, which will end '-is' remove the '-is', leaving you with the stem add the endings shown below

E.g. Nom sing. Gen sing. Stem

Caput. capitis capit

Canalis canalis canal

It is necessary to use the stem while declining the nouns in further cases - Abl.sing, Nom.plur, Gen.plur, Abl.plur.

The Gender of nouns is determined by endings of Nom.Sing.

Exceptions to the rule:

Mater, matris, f - meninx

Gaster, gastris, f - stomach

Mater, matris, f is used in the following terms of nouns in feminine gender.

- Dura mater- hard meninx,
- Pia mater - soft meninx

- Arachnoidea mater
- arachnoidal meninx

Examples for Nouns of the 3-d declension (femininum)

- 1- Auris, is f. Ear
- 2- Basis, is f. Base
- 3- Cavitas, atis f.- Cavity
- 4- Cervix, icis f.- Neck (neck of uterus, bladder, tooth)
- 5- Frons, frontis f.- Forehead
- 6- Gl.parotis, tidis f.- Parotid gland
- 7- Meninx, ngis f.- Meninx
- 8- Radix, icis f.- Root
- 9- Pelvis, is f. - Pelvis , Pelvis renalis – renal pelvis
- 10- Pyramis, idis f.- Pyramid
- 11- Tuberositas, atis f.- Tuberosity
- 12- Bilis, is f. -Bile
- 13- Extremitas, atis f. - End of long organs
- 14- Empressio, ionis f.- Impression
- 15- Iris, idis f.- Iris
- 16- Lens, lentis f.- Lens
- 17- Phalanx, ngis f.- Phalanx
- 18- Pubes, is f. Mons, publis.

Conclusion. A good bet for a Latin noun whose nominative singular ends in -a is that it is a feminine noun of the First Declension. Likewise, a noun ending in -us in the nominative singular is likely Second Declension masculine. There are exceptions, but guessing those is a good starting place. It's not so easy when you get the nouns belonging to the Third Declension.

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